

Humanitarian Data Exchange

Description

The United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs launched the Humanitarian Data Exchange (HDX) in mid-2014 in an effort to collect, analyse and coordinate data generated by multiple sources when responding to a large-scale humanitarian crisis. Accurate, timely standardised and easily accessible data is vital to decision makers during a disaster and the HDX platform allows for collection in one location in addition to data visualisation tools to aid in response planning.

The HDX has been used to respond to the Ebola crisis in West Africa in 2014, the Nepal earthquake in 2015, food security issues in Yemen in 2015 and the global impact of El Nino throughout 2015 and 2016. The datasets enable aid workers and government decision makers to have access to the same information and provide more targeted and specific interventions in local communities depending on conditions and need. The HDX is envisioned as potentially evolving into a social sharing platform where users can not only share open source data but engage in collaborative problem solving and develop crowdsourced, data driven solutions to complex humanitarian crises.

Economic benefits

Aid agencies, international organisations and local governments are able to target relief efforts and designate limited resources in ways that will best meet the needs of local communities. Access to standardised information also reduces service duplication and eliminates redundancy, saving money that can be spent on other important goods and services. Funds can be prioritized and redirected to areas where they have the greatest impact.

Health/social benefits

Easily accessible data that is both standardised and user-friendly enables decision makers to track measures like food price, and local and national economic output that are impacted by humanitarian crises, addressing the downstream consequences of large scale disaster before they have considerable impact on the population. Coordinated data use also enables faster and more effective aid interventions, mitigating some of the associated risks that accompany humanitarian operations and ongoing recovery operations.

Supporting links

<https://data.hdx.rwllabs.org/>

Accessed 14 May 2016.

'UN agencies boost partnership on visualization of food security data for Yemen' http://bit.ly/Food_Security_Data
Accessed 14 May 2016.

'Humanitarian data: OCHA launches ground-breaking data exchange platform'
http://bit.ly/OCHA_Launches_Data_Exchange
Accessed 14 May 2016.

http://bit.ly/Humanitarian_Data_Exchange
Accessed 14 May 2016.